

Quantum Partition Function and Statistical Potential versus Time Reversal Elastic Two-Body Scattering Balance

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 24, 2020

In a previous note (1) we argued the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions may be obtained directly from a time reversal elastic two-body scattering balance. The quantum “effects” of fermions and bosons appear directly in the scattering balance with no need for entropy, counting or partition function calculations. The quantum effects are incorporated into the kinematics. This is consistent with a generalized approach developed by Kaniadakis (2), although he calculates an entropy function rather than obtain the distribution directly from the reaction balance. In another note, we argued that the grand canonical partition function calculations of the FD and BE distributions are based on the idea that $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$, where u is the chemical potential, does not really represent a “particle”, but is a “second” probability which follows from the reaction balance. Thus, one needs to perform a second calculation (i.e. the grand canonical partition function calculation) to obtain the first probability, namely the number of particles with energy e_i .

These ideas seem to raise a question regarding the use of the quantum partition function, namely $\text{Trace}(\exp(-1/T K))$, if K , the kinetic energy operator is the full Hamiltonian. In the calculation of the trace, the symmetry or antisymmetry of the wavefunction is considered and one obtains (as a first limit beyond a classical limit) a statistical potential. (3). We have argued the symmetry of the wavefunction is already used in establishing the time reversal elastic two body scattering balance and this balance justifies the use of $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$, but not applied to a particle. (It is used in the sense of the grand canonical distribution where the presence of n bosons in a state has the probability $\exp(-n(e_i-u)/T)$). Thus, it seems unusual one would involve a Trace and make use of the symmetry of wavefunction which applies to particles which seems to be a different type of calculation. In this note, we attempt to clarify these ideas.

Time Reversal Elastic Two Body Scattering Balance

We have previously argued one may directly obtain the FD and BE distributions directly from a balanced two body elastic reaction. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, this balance is:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking the \ln of both sides of ((1b)) and equating to ((1a)) yields the MB distribution.

For the case of fermions and bosons, quantum considerations come into play. For a fermion, e_1 cannot scatter into e_3 if it is occupied. Thus, we suggest the balance to be:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1-f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1-f(e_2)] \quad ((2))$$

Here we consider both the forward and reversed reactions of ((1a)). Taking the ln of both sides of ((2)) and equating to ((1a)) yields:

$$\ln[f(e_i) / (1-f(e_i))] = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((3))$$

From this one obtains the FD distribution. For the case of bosons, Feynman (4) has shown that the scattering of a boson e_1 into a set n bosons with energy e_3 (with no statistical mechanics, but with quantum mechanics) yields an enhancement of $n+1$. Thus, we suggest:

$$f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1+f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1+f(e_2)] \quad ((4))$$

Taking the ln of ((4)) and equating to ((1a)) yields the BE distribution. Note, $1+f(e_i)$ appears in the boson equation, while in the BE distribution one has $1/(1-\exp(-1/T(e-u)))$. This is because one has function-inverse function pairs which is consistent with a generalized theory developed by Kaniadakis (2). We use the generalized result:

$$\ln(k(f(e))) = -1/T (e-u) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } k \text{ is a function arising from kinematics.}$$

For the fermion or boson case, it arises from the quantum mechanical kinematics.

Taking the exponential of both sides of ((5)) yields: $k(f(e)) = \exp(-1/T(e-u))$. For the MB case, k is the identity function and $\exp(-1/T(e-u))$ applies to a particle. In other cases, it seems to be a second probability. This second probability may be used to calculate the average number of particles. For fermions, one has:

$$\{ 1 \exp(-1/T(e-u)) + 0 \exp(-1/T(e-u)) \} / \{ \exp(-1/T(e-u)) + \exp(-1/T(e-u)) \} \quad ((6))$$

This is the FD distribution. For bosons, a similar expression applies.

Partition Function Approach

It seems statistical mechanics makes much use of partition functions. In (5), we have tried to argue that such an approach maps into the time reversal elastic two particle scattering balance. This two particle scattering approach already contains quantum effects for fermions and bosons. Furthermore, $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ does not seem to apply as the probability of a quantum particle, but rather is associated with $k(f(e))$.

As a result, it seems unusual a quantum mechanical Trace $[\exp(-1/T K)]$ is used together with the symmetry or antisymmetry of the wavefunction. It seems if one uses generalized kinematics (i.e. two body elastic scattering balances), quantum symmetry has already been considered. Furthermore, we argue one has to be careful as $\exp(-H/T)$, where H is the Hamiltonian, may not describe the probability weight of a system of quantum particles. It may be associated with the weight of a kind of modified object. For example, for fermions:

$$f(e) / (1-f(e)) = \exp(-1/T (e-u)) \quad \text{and for bosons } f(e) / (1+ f(e)) = \exp(-1/T (e-u))$$

In general, $\exp(-H/T)$, which applies to a system in an ensemble (it seems), is broken into single particle terms, $\exp(-\epsilon_i/T)$, as if these were the probability weights of different single particles, multiplied together in an “and” probability situation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have previously suggested Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions may be directly obtained from a time reversal elastic two body scattering balance. There is no need for entropy, counting or partition functions in such an approach. Such a balance already incorporates symmetry properties of the wavefunction for fermions and bosons. Furthermore, it seems there is a second probability in the problem, namely $\exp(-(\epsilon-u)/T)$. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, this applies directly to particles, but for the fermions and bosons it does not seem to do so. Thus, we point out a possible inconsistency between the quantum partition function $\text{Trace}(\exp(-H/T))$ which leads to a statistical potential and the approach of balanced two body scattering. If the $\text{Trace}(\exp(-H/T))$ led directly to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions, then it seems there would be no inconsistency, but it seems that the calculation is different.

References

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